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ON

“IMPACT OF COVID-19 ON SUSTAINABLE
DEVELOPMENT”

In Collaboration with

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ON

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As Z score value is more than critical value null hypothesis is rejected and alternate hypothesis is accepted. Therefore, waiting time has some importance while eating fast food.

HYPOTHESIS 5

H0=While eating fast food, Importance of variety of menu is less than or equal to average

H1=While eating fast food, Importance of variety of menu is greater than average.

Population mean μ	3	
Sample mean \bar{X}	3.511811024	
Standard deviation σ	1.356150842	
Number of samples N	127	11.26942767
Numerator $\bar{X}-\mu$	0.511811024	
Denominator $\sigma \div \sqrt{N}$	0.120338928	
z score	4.253079474	
Alpha value α	0.05	
Critical value	1.65	
z score > critical value		

$4.25 > 1.65$

H0 is rejected and H1 is accepted.

As Zscore value is more than critical value null hypothesis is rejected and alternate hypothesis is accepted. Therefore, variety of menu is important factor while eating fast food.

HYPOTHESIS 6

H0=While eating fast food, Importance of Hygiene and cleanliness is less than or equal to average

H1=While eating fast food, Importance of Hygiene and cleanliness is greater than average.

Population mean μ	3	
Sample mean \bar{X}	4.023622047	
Standard deviation σ	1.422408905	
Number of samples N	127	11.26942767
Numerator $\bar{X}-\mu$	1.023622047	
Denominator $\sigma \div \sqrt{N}$	0.12621838	
z score	8.109928572	
Alpha value α	0.05	
Critical value	1.65	
z score > critical value		

$8.11 > 1.65$

H0 is rejected and H1 is accepted.

As Z score value is more than critical value null hypothesis is rejected and alternate hypothesis is accepted. Therefore, hygiene and cleanliness are more important factor while eating fast food.

HYPOTHESIS 7

H0=While eating fast food, Importance of Social distancing is less than or equal to average

H1=While eating fast food, Importance of Social distancing is greater than average.

Population mean μ	3	
Sample mean \bar{X}	4.039370079	
Standard deviation σ	1.444208878	
Number of samples N	127	11.26942767

Numerator $\bar{X}-\mu$	1.039370079	
Denominator $\sigma \div \sqrt{N}$	0.128152815	
z score	8.110396013	
Alpha value α	0.05	
Critical value	1.65	
z score > critical value		

$8.11 > 1.65$

H0 is rejected and H1 is accepted.

As Z score value is more than critical value null hypothesis is rejected and alternate hypothesis is accepted. Therefore, social distancing is more important factor while eating fast food.

HYPOTHESIS 8

H0=While eating fast food, Importance of Sanitization is less than or equal to average

H1=While eating fast food, Importance of sanitization is greater than average.

Population mean μ	3	
Sample mean \bar{X}	4.086614173	
Standard deviation σ	1.43108141	
Number of samples N	127	11.26942767
Numerator $\bar{X}-\mu$	1.086614173	
Denominator $\sigma \div \sqrt{N}$	0.12698794	
z score	8.556829645	
Alpha value α	0.05	
Critical value	1.65	
z score > critical value		

$8.56 > 1.65$

H0 is rejected and H1 is accepted. As Z score value is more than critical value null hypothesis is rejected and alternate hypothesis is accepted. Therefore, sanitization is more important factor while eating fast food.

As all above factors are important while eating fast food, it is necessary to find out most important factors while eating fast food. Therefore, in the following table ranking has done for all the factors based on their z test value.

Table 1

Ranking of factors based on Z test value

Factors	Mean Value	Std. Dev.	Z Test Value	Rank
Food quality and taste	3.77	1.47	5.9	3
Ambience	3.29	1.29	2.6	7
Service quality	3.68	1.38	5.53	4
Waiting time	3.37	1.25	3.33	6
Variety in menu	3.51	1.35	4.25	5
Hygiene and cleanliness	4.02	1.42	8.11	2
Social Distancing	4.03	1.44	8.11	2
Sanitization	4.09	1.43	8.56	1

As per above analysis and testing, due to covid 19, in the future people will give more importance to sanitization, social distancing and hygiene and cleanliness while choosing fast food outlet. Earlier food quality and taste had 1st priority while choosing fast food outlet. But now this priority has changed because of covid 19.

FINDINGS

From above analysis and testing following are the findings:

1. 98.4% of the respondents are from the age group of 18 to 25years. As they are youngsters, almost everybody like to have fast-food. They prefer to have both vegetarian as well as non-vegetarian food from outside.
2. Majority of the respondents prefer to eat fast-food at least once in a week. As they are youngsters more than 65% respondents prefer to visit fast food outlet with their friends. They prefer to have fast food in the evening time. Majority spend around Rs. 500/- per visit.
3. These youngsters get to know about fast food outlets mainly through word of mouth or via social media. z score of 5.90, which is greater than critical value implies that while eating fast food, food quality and taste is the important factor. Before covid 19 they were giving priority to food quality and taste while choosing fast food outlet.
4. During covid 19 their number of visits to fast food outlet are decreased. They are giving more preference to homemade food and balanced diet. But they will prefer to eat from fast food outlet after Covid 19. Their frequency to visit these outlets will be reduced and they will prefer to place order and get the parcel delivered at home.
5. In post Covid 19 in case if they will go outside to eat, they will give more importance to sanitization, social distancing and Hygiene and cleanliness while choosing fast food outlet. Calculation of z test value and ranking of the parameters based on z test value (Table 1) shows that rank 1 is assigned to sanitization, rank 2 to social distancing, hygiene and cleanliness, rank 3 to food quality and taste, rank 4 to service quality, rank 5 to variety in menu, rank 6 to waiting time and rank 7 to ambience. Prior to Covid 19 pandemic, food quality and taste had 1st priority while choosing fast food outlet. The preferences of youngsters have changed because of Covid 19.

CONCLUSION

Fast food is priority food for youngster and they enjoy to eat that food with their friends. During the Covid 19 period their frequency to eat fast-food has decreased but they will not stop eating fast-food in the future. With proper care, hygiene and sanitization and social distancing norms they will prefer to go out and eat fast food. These fast-food outlets can do their business if they will give importance to sanitization, social distancing and hygiene at their outlet. In future the young consumers will prefer to eat fast food at their place, therefore fast delivery of the parcels with due care will also be significant to scale up the business of these fast-food joints.

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IMPACT OF COVID-19 ANNOUNCEMENT ON NIFTY 50

Mr. Shahid AnsariAssistant Professor, Clara's College of Commerce

ABSTRACT:

The NIFTY 50 is an index diversified across many sectors of the nation's economy. Covid 19 affected not only human beings but also all sectors of the economy. All the stock markets across the globe are highly affected. From approximately index 12000, the index fell sharply to 7500, and then rose again in February to 15000, representing a significant gain for the Nifty 50.

The Nifty 50 doubled in a very short period of time, barely 11 months, or less than a year. Covid 19 announcement and lockdown brought the opportunities and challenges together. Falling Nifty 50, rush to book a profit, then rush to buy a valuable stock at a penny price. This recovery of Nifty 50 was unexpected during this pandemic situation. Some stocks can increase by 100%, 200%, 300%, or even more. The behaviour of the index, buying and selling, top gainer and top loser, and top gainer and top loser were the factors influencing the study of the Nifty 50.

Keywords: Nifty 50, NSE, Sensex, Index, Covid-19.

INTRODUCTION:

At the very first, Covid 19 was announced and a few days later, lockdown was announced by the government of India for the period of 21 days in the month of March 2020. This lockdown continued for more than six months, then unlocking began phase wise. A lockdown means a complete shutdown. People are forced to stay at home except for a few involved in necessary services like health care workers, municipality services and a few essential commodity stores. The reason behind this lockdown was an unknown disease – Covid 19. The year 2020 will be remembered for the global pandemic, which affected everything on this earth.

Like everything, the stock market was also falling. Before the announcement of the lockdown, Nifty 50 was at 12000. On 24th March 2020, Nifty 50 was around at 7500. This continuous falling trend of Nifty 50 during the lockdown forced people to sell their holdings. People sold their stock and booked a profit. Within two months, the Nifty 50 gradually began to rise, which was unexpected, and it eventually reached 15000 in February 2021. From 7500 to 15000, the index is the story from billionaire to beggar and vice versa.

LITERATURE REVIEW:

1. Dr. T C Thomas, Dr. G Sankararaman, & Dr. S Suresh (2020) in the research paper “IMPACT OF COVID-19 ANNOUNCEMENTS ON NIFTY STOCKS” finds that because of Covid-19 Announcements on NIFTY Stocks, financial performance varied among various sectors. The financial sector noted the highest negative return, followed by the pharmaceutical sector. Although all the sectors have reported negative performance, sectors like fertilizers and services provided the highest mean return. During the preceding period, government packages accelerated the stock market.
2. M Pushpalatha, J Srinivasan & G Shanmugapriya (2019) in the study “A Research on Volatility in the Indian Stock Market with Special Reference to Nifty and Selected companies of financial Service Sector of NSE researcher found that there was sufficient proof which indicate the varying volatility which showed sign of clustering, high persistence and predictability. Nifty, NSE Nifty and Nifty 50 of selected companies of financial service sector was weak and moves randomly during the study period. The stock market was regaining efficiently because of improved technology, regulations and retail participation.
3. M Praveen Kumar & N V Manoj Kumara (2020) in his study “Market capitalization: Pre and post COVID-19 analysis” studied Indian stock market behaviors during Covid 19, movement of the stock market during the pre and post Covid 19 situation. Performance of stocks during the spike period and discovered that such drastic movement in the stock market is due to covid 19, and the availability of covid 19 vaccine will stabilize the market. It is also stated that the stock market will be stable after the end of lockdown and Covid 19.
4. Divyang J Joshi & Pratik H Bhavasker (2020) their research publication “Predicting Nifty 50 Movement Use of Advance Decline Ratio” state that volatility in the stock market affects the trading pattern of investors. Prediction of the trade market is very crucial and requires deep analysis and continuous study. An investment advisor helps people with picking up stocks. The Researchers also focused on the